

Inclusive Metadata Toolkit

Cultural Assessment Working Group

Digital Library Federation

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1. Introduction

There has been a rising interest in inclusive metadata within libraries and archives communities because of the increasing recognition of the ways that traditional descriptive practices have contributed to an inequitable knowledge landscape and less effective discovery and usage of resources. However, despite ample academic literature and popular discussions on the topic, it can still be difficult for metadata professionals to find concrete ways to incorporate inclusive metadata principles into their daily work practices.

This Toolkit is a collection of resources, software tools, and case studies intended to provide support for folks who want to promote and implement inclusive metadata practices in their work and at their organizations. The overall Toolkit contains two components:

1. The [Inclusive Metadata Toolkit Resources Directory](#), which is sortable/filterable by a set of parameters such as topic area, metadata type, resource type, and more.
2. This **Inclusive Metadata Toolkit guide document**, which provides context for the listed resources and makes them easier to use and navigate.

This Toolkit guide document is expected to be static, unless significant revisions are deemed necessary. We hope that the Toolkit Resources Directory will be an ongoing collaborative resource that practitioners will add to over time. To this end, we encourage Toolkit readers to [propose additions via this form](#). We are especially interested in collecting practice case studies to support ongoing sharing of information around common challenges.

Inclusive and Reparative Metadata

Inclusive metadata describes an approach to descriptive metadata that is grounded in empathy, care, and respect, and aware of the historical and ongoing inequalities that shape the knowledge landscape. Inclusive metadata work seeks to employ a wider range of perspectives that have been traditionally excluded from and silenced in descriptive practices, in order to more accurately recognize, represent, and respect the breadth of human experiences. An example of an inclusive metadata practice is choosing a more accurate and preferred term used by a community to describe itself rather than a vague, incorrect, or even derogatory established authority term when describing archival materials representing that community.

Reparative metadata addresses the impact of oppressive and harmful descriptive norms and practices by implementing inclusive metadata principles in the assessment and remediation of existing and legacy metadata. An example of a reparative metadata project is identifying materials in an anthropological collection labeled with an offensive or derogatory name for a community, and adding the current preferred term for that community to those materials and a contextualizing statement to the collection about why harmful language was retained in the collection as evidence of the archive's role in the colonial project.

1.1 Toolkit Sections

This Toolkit Guide is intended to be flexible, and you can start with any section depending on your individual and institutional needs. Each section contextualizes a particular area of work, offers ideas of where to start, and highlights a few selected resources. The full [Inclusive Metadata Toolkit Resources Directory](#) provides a filterable and sortable spreadsheet of all resources.

Learning about Inclusive Metadata Work presents a selection of resources for practitioners at all different levels of knowledge and engagement to learn more about inclusive metadata concepts.

Strategies for Advancing Inclusive Metadata outlines considerations for advocacy and activism around inclusive metadata, including key questions to ask and concrete strategies for action.

Assessment and Remediation Frameworks, Software Tools for Metadata Assessment and Remediation, Controlled Vocabularies, and Harmful Language and Content Statements provide tools for implementing inclusive metadata practices across various stages of the digital object life cycle.

1.2 Toolkit contributors

This toolkit was developed between 2020 and 2024 by the Inclusive Metadata Task Force of the Digital Library Federation (DLF) Cultural Assessment Working Group (CAWG), which was co-led by Morgan McKeehan, Rachel Jane Wittman, and Alexandra Provo with support from CAWG co-chairs over the years (Hannah Skates Kettler, Jenny Bradshaw, Alexandra Provo, and Jackson Huang).

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2. Learning about Inclusive Metadata Work

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Learning](#) resources.

The “Learning” group of Resources were selected with the aim of providing an introduction for anyone who would like to learn more about the primary issues within inclusive metadata work.

As a whole, these Resources are meant to provide an overview of broad concepts and challenges. Additional tags for levels and topics were also assigned with the intention of making it easier for readers to choose an area to focus on.

2.1 Tags: “Learning - Level” and “Spark”

“Learning - Level” tags are assigned only to the Learning group. These levels are meant to give users a sense of what to expect from a resource, or to help with deciding where to start within a topic area.

- **foundational:** introduces terms and concepts, or outlines general guidelines within a broad area. Meant to provide an approachable orientation to a topic.
- **intermediate:** Focused explorations of theories and tools within a particular topic area. These build on basic concepts or propose new approaches to common challenges.
- **advanced:** More specialized, in-depth examinations, such as case studies. Ideally, these provide examples of “how-to do this” for a specific topic.
- **“spark”:** shorter articles that can serve as conversation starters for reading groups or to share with stakeholders when pitching a project. These can be found across the Learning levels.

2.2 Topics

Learning resources were selected to cover a range of topics inclusive metadata work frequently aims to address, with the following categories:

- Disability
- Gender and sexuality
- Indigenous sovereignty
- Privacy
- Race and ethnicity
- Religion/spiritual practices
- User-facing communications about materials and description (such as content warnings/about archival description)

3. Strategies for Advancing Inclusive Metadata

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Strategies for Advancing Inclusive Metadata](#) resources.

This section provides recommendations on strategies for advocating for change, while recognizing that advocacy may need to be balanced with operational and personal considerations specific to your situation. Which approaches are sustainable will depend on the current level of institutional support for inclusive metadata activities, as well as broader local, state, and national contexts. For example, there may be laws in your state regarding funding or support for diversity, equity, and inclusion work. Also consider the status of who will lead such projects and if there are protections for this work due to academic freedom. Another factor to consider is personal trauma that may come from engaging in inclusive or reparative metadata work, including exposure to harmful metadata or content.

The goal of this section is to support metadata practitioners working to manage capacity and secure resources for meaningful engagement in inclusive metadata work. Advocacy strives to give our work broader impact throughout the galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM) field by increasing visibility, supporting challenging conversations, and providing a roadmap for others.

3.1 Key Questions

Working through how these questions apply to your local context may be helpful for developing feasible strategies and gaining traction:

- How does a particular institution, community, or field perceive itself? What does it value and what does it consider risky?
- How do you tailor the language used to discuss inclusive metadata work to resonate with the people you are trying to convince of the value of this work?
- What risks are involved for practitioners engaged in inclusive metadata work, and how do you mitigate and address these risks?
- What resources are needed to engage in this work in a way that creates sustainable impact?

3.2 Advocacy in Different Contexts

Advocacy for inclusive metadata work can occur in institutional, community, and field-wide contexts. Strategies for each of these contexts may have unique considerations, but there are also significant areas of overlap.

Here are some actions that can be effective within multiple contexts, with some tailoring for audience:

- Host a webinar, film screening, reading group, or discussion on inclusive metadata
- Create an interest or working group to discuss how to integrate these concerns/awareness into existing metadata workflows, processes, etc.
- Publish an article, white paper, blog post, etc. about your work

3.2.1 *Institutional*

As a metadata practitioner, you may be able to implement certain inclusive metadata practices on your own within the scope of your job responsibilities, while others may require administrative approval or buy-in from other stakeholders – internal advocacy within your institution. A successful project of the first type, such as updating legacy metadata to match recently changed Library of Congress subject headings (e.g. “Slaves” to “Enslaved Persons”), can make it easier to gain support for projects of the second, such as overriding problematic LCSH terms with local alternatives.

In addition to gaining the support of administrators, advocacy with colleagues increases collaborators for projects and shifts cultural norms to make inclusive metadata practices a more accepted and established aspect of work at your institution. Gathering feedback from users through an online form or other avenues can also surface issues and provide external pressure to make changes.

3.2.2 Local communities

Engaging directly with a community represented by your materials is a way to build trust and ensure your efforts are in line with the wishes of those impacted by your institution's metadata. These kinds of relationships are a commitment, and it's important to consider continuity in the face of staff turnover or change, compensation for community members' participation, and accountability measures to ensure there is follow-up and communication about any actions taken.

3.2.3 Across the field

Working cross-institutionally in the field can occur at the state, national, or international level, or more locally. Work in these wider contexts can broaden impact and provide authority for shaping local levels, but can be slower, since ensuring any changes address the needs of both specific institutions and the larger group takes more work.

Highlighted Resource: Evaluating your Capacity for Advocacy

The [IFLA Advocacy Capacities Grid](#) is a framework that can be used to support organizations in evaluating their current advocacy capabilities across core activity areas. The tool's purpose is to help organizations use time and resources effectively by identifying strengths, gaps, and priorities for focused effort.

3.3 Examples of Inclusive Metadata Initiatives

Some ideas for inclusive metadata initiatives include:

Initiative	Examples
<i>Create a local controlled vocabulary (see the Controlled Vocabularies section of this Toolkit).</i>	Heather M. Campbell, Christopher S. Dieckman, Nausicaa L. Rose, and Harriet E. Wintermute's article " Improving Subject Headings for Iowa Indigenous Peoples "
<i>Identify harmful terminology and locate it in your metadata (see the Assessment and Remediation Frameworks and Software Tools for Assessment and Remediation sections of this Toolkit)</i>	Make a list of problematic terms relevant to your collections or draw from a list like Problem LCSH and search on keywords known to be offensive in your collections
<i>Host webinar or film screenings or a discussion session</i>	Change the Subject, Incorporating Critical Cataloging into Your Work

Initiative	Examples
<i>Create an interest or working group to discuss how to integrate these concerns/awareness into existing metadata workflows, processes, etc.</i>	Inclusive Metadata Task Force (Cultural Assessment Working Group, DLF)
<i>Start a reading group</i>	Suggest readings from the Learning section
<i>Apply shared guidelines on replacing harmful or outdated terms in descriptive metadata, for example updating controlled vocabulary terms, using alternative controlled vocabularies, or revising problematic and/or aggrandizing language</i>	Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia (A4BLiP) , Anti-Racist Description Resources , Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources , Best Practices for Queer Metadata (see sections on Controlled Vocabularies and Software Tools for Assessment and Remediation for additional examples)
<i>Create institutional-level inclusive metadata guidelines, style guides, or internal documentation for metadata best practices</i>	Yale records on Japanese American incarceration during World War II , Harvard's Joint Processing Guidelines: Reparative Description , Wilson Special Collections Library's Guide to Conscious Editing
<i>Write a statement or policy on harmful language in your collections (see the Harmful Language and Content Statements section of this Toolkit).</i>	Cataloging Lab's list of statements on bias in library and archives description
<i>Create a feedback form so harmful language or other inclusive metadata issues can be surfaced</i>	NYU Libraries' Changing the Subject project and harmful language reporting form
<i>Facilitate a conversation, focus group, user study, or other collaborative project with partners and community members represented in, or impacted by, your metadata to learn more about their values, use cases, concerns, problematic language, or priorities.</i>	Amelia Bowen Koford's article " Engaging an Author in a Critical Reading of Subject Headings "

Table 1: List of inclusive metadata initiative ideas and examples.

4. Assessment and Remediation Frameworks

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Assessment and Remediation Frameworks](#) resources.

While recommendations for assessing metadata quality and strategies for remediation are well-established, the concept of "inclusivity" has not been explicitly included in these frameworks.

Applying the lens of inclusivity to existing metadata assessment and remediation frameworks can help develop benchmarks within each criteria that are relevant to the specific context you are addressing.

4.1 Adapting Metadata Quality Characteristics to Assess Inclusivity

Drawn from Bruce and Hillman’s 2004 book chapter “The Continuum of Metadata Quality: Defining, Expressing, Exploiting,” the characteristics of completeness, accuracy, conformance to expectations, consistency, timeliness, and accessibility are widely used in the GLAM field to assess metadata quality. While these criteria are commonly applied to overall metadata quality, they can also be adapted to assess the inclusivity of metadata practices.

Metadata Quality Characteristics - General & Inclusive		
Criterion	General Assessment	Assessing for Inclusivity
Completeness	Is the metadata element, property, and/or attribute present?	To what extent does collections metadata represent the people within the communities the collections are from? Who is represented, who is missing, what are the areas of gaps?
Accuracy	Are metadata values semantically and syntactically correct?	Is the correct terminology, spelling, diacritical markers, and punctuation used for names and labels?
Conformance to Expectations	Do the metadata values adhere to the expectations of your defined user communities (internal and external)?	Are the terms preferred by the communities represented used in the descriptive metadata? Are the most current subject headings used?
Consistency	Are semantic and structural values and elements represented in a consistent manner across records? Are values consistent within your domain?	Once identified, are updated or preferred terms and concepts used consistently in the metadata?

Metadata Quality Characteristics - General & Inclusive		
Criterion	General Assessment	Assessing for Inclusivity
Timeliness	Do you assess metadata from legacy projects or systems before reusing it?	Language changes over time and terms that were once preferred or commonly used can become harmful. Are there known legacy collections that need remediation work? Is there a schedule for assessing metadata (e.g., every 10-20 years)?
Accessibility	Can metadata be read by humans and machines?	Is metadata description written in plain language? Is metadata provided in the appropriate language(s)? Are metadata elements that provide information about accessibility features or hazards present?

Table 2. Table translating general metadata quality characteristics to inclusive quality characteristics

Highlighted Resource: Accessibility metadata

The [User Experience Guide for Displaying Accessibility Metadata 1.0](#) summary post from Accessible Libraries summarizes a W3C guide that defines various accessibility metadata properties intended for digital publications.

4.2 Assessing the Broader Impacts of Inclusive Metadata Work

In addition to directly addressing metadata quality, inclusive metadata work can have broader social, community, and organizational impacts. Ricky Punzalan identifies the following “Areas of Impact” in his talk, [“Words Matter: Reparative Description as Decolonial Action”](#):

- **Knowledge:** New knowledge about collections is generated and collections are used in meaningful ways across diverse settings.
- **Attitudes:** Staff attitudes and practices have shifted and community members feel more welcome interacting with collections and staff.

- **Professional discourse:** Staff have a new understanding of responsibilities and “ownership” of collections.
- **Institutional capacity:** Guidelines for reparative/inclusive practices and new ways of managing collections have been developed.
- **Policy:** New policies around collections care and representation are in progress or in place.
- **Relationships:** Reciprocal relationships between institutions and community members are forming or in place.

5. Software Tools for Assessment and Remediation

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Software Tools for Assessment and Remediation](#) resources.

Reparative work on legacy description to identify and remediate problematic language in finding aids and/or digital collections metadata can be an iterative and multi-layered process.

Areas potentially needing regular maintenance include, but are not limited to:

- Routine changes to vocabularies for subject headings, demographic terms, and/or keywords (coming from the vocabulary’s maintainer)
- Changes in form of name of creators, contributors, or human subjects per preferred authority files
- Changes to geographic location names, especially derogatory name changes
- Changes to classification schedules used by the collections
- Local changes made (if applicable: is the change still valid, does the reason for the local change exist) or local systems created to supplement controlled data
- Uncontrolled descriptive metadata (esp. Digital Collections: Title, description; Archives: scope and content notes, historical notes, etc.)

There are a number of resources and software tools that can aid in reparative descriptive work, particularly with finding, identifying, and remediating metadata and description at scale. This section focuses on low-overhead software tools that are useful for conducting systematic and reproducible metadata audits and assessments, and for building more manageable workflows for prioritizing, tracking, and implementing the many types of changes that may be required.

5.1 Assessment Tools: Identifying Problematic Terms for Remediation Workflows

The following tools and resources were developed to address specific assessment needs within reparative metadata work, such as for analyzing collections and generating reports. These tools can help you determine where harmful language occurs in your metadata, and what records or terms to target for reparative work. Using specialized applications or scripts to automate parts of the

assessment and remediation process can be helpful for running batch operations across large numbers of records when working with collections at scale.

For auditing Dublin Core or other metadata schemas in CSV format:

- [Marriott Reparative Metadata Assessment Tool \(MaRMAT\)](#)
 - This tool provides a graphic user interface for generating assessment reports on CSV-based metadata. The user can select from included lexicons based on harmful language and outdated/problematic LCSH terms, or can run the tool against a user created lexicon.
- [mrs - Noah Geraci](#)
 - This python script identifies instances where women are labeled by their husbands name, by identifying instances where a name follows the structure "Mrs. [male first name] [last name]." It outputs a report of names as a CSV.

For auditing EAD finding aids and MARC XML:

- [Description Audit Tool - Duke University Libraries](#)
 - This tool is designed to query descriptive metadata in EAD and MARCXML files against a pre-configured set of harmful terms. Tool includes binaries, documentation, and source code for public use. Repository also includes a lexicon which lists possible offensive keywords.

5.2 User-friendly Data Manipulation Tools

For getting started with batch data manipulation and analysis, here are three good options for easy-to-use, graphic user interface-based tools. These are accessible for folks who are not familiar with running scripts or using a command-line interface.

- [OpenRefine](#)
 - Free, open-source data analysis and manipulation tool
- [MarcEdit](#)
 - Free desktop tool to batch edit MARC data
- [LibreOffice Calc](#)
 - Free spreadsheet tool that can find and resolve character encoding issues and helpful for format conversion

For more metadata assessment tools, see the [DLF Metadata Working Group Tools list](#).

6. Controlled Vocabularies

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Controlled Vocabularies](#) resources.

While controlled vocabularies are harder to change than free-text descriptions since they often require proposals and vetting, editing or proposing new terms has been a key activity in inclusive metadata practice because of the field-wide impact it has.

6.1 Proposing Changes to Library of Congress Controlled Vocabularies

The Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) is a widely-used controlled vocabulary in both MARC-based systems and in digital collections, and its terms are often a focus of intervention. Changing LCSH involves a formal proposal process, typically conducted via the Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC). Even if your organization is not a PCC member, there are several pathways to get involved in submitting proposals, such as contacting a SACO Funnel, collaborating via the Cataloging Lab, or contacting dedicated groups in professional organizations such as ARLIS/NA's Cataloging Advisory Committee.

Examples of groups collaborating on Library of Congress Subject Heading proposals:

- [SACO Funnels contact list](#)
 - SACO Funnels are groups of catalogers with shared expertise to pool their efforts in developing and submitting proposals. These groups can be joined or contacted directly to suggest subject proposal topics. Funnels coalesce around various categories, including regional, material form, discipline, and identity.
- [Cataloging Lab](#)
 - The Cataloging Lab is a collaborative project whose goal is to connect catalogers interested in working together on subject and name authority proposals. One of the aims is to demystify the proposal process, get people with interest in a specific topic connected with those with proposal submission experience, and help people create proposals likely to be approved. Proposals are reviewed by the Cataloging Lab community. The Cataloging Lab also curates a crowdsourced lists of problematic subject headings, Problem LCSH (<https://cataloginglab.org/problem-lcsh/>)
- [Proposed changes to problematic art-related subject headings](#)
 - The Cataloging Advisory Committee of ARLIS/NA solicits suggestions for subject heading change proposals specifically related to art, architecture, design, and related fields.

Highlighted Resource: Proposing Changes to Library of Congress Controlled Vocabularies

[Creating subject headings for Indigenous topics: a culturally respectful guide](#) provides guidance on creating subject heading proposals for Indigenous topics that can be submitted via the Subject Authority Cooperative Program (SACO) for addition to the Library of Congress Subject Headings.

6.2 Using non-LCSH Controlled Vocabularies

While Library of Congress Subject Headings are widely used, not all subjects are covered comprehensively, and there are many options for alternative controlled vocabularies for specific areas. Additionally, besides subject headings, genre terms may include harmful or community-specific terminology and can be used on their own or in conjunction with statements on harmful language and content in digital and archival collections to point to prejudicial materials. Many alternatives to LCSH were created with extensive community input and provide a more respectful and thorough range of terms. Some examples include:

- [African Studies Thesaurus](#)
 - Released by the library staff at African Studies Centre Leiden, provides a structured list of English terms covering African studies with an emphasis on the social sciences and humanities.
- [First Nations, Metis and Inuit – Indigenous Ontologies \(FNMIIO\)](#)
 - Released through the National Indigenous Knowledge and Language Alliance (NIKLA) and represents an initial effort to improve the representation of Indigenous peoples and communities in libraries, archives and other cultural memory institutions.
- [Homosaurus](#)
 - An international linked data vocabulary of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer (LGBTQ) terms.
- [National Indian Boarding School Healing Coalition \(NIBSDA\) Tribal Name Authority Files](#)
 - This list includes information on 574 Tribal Nations in the United States, including current names and historical variant names as they appear in the historic record.
- [University of British Columbia \(BC\) Xwi7xwa Library's Indigenous Knowledge Organization](#)
 - This includes the "Names for BC First Nations in BC List" which is regularly updated to reflect community usage.

- [RBMS Controlled Vocabulary for Rare Materials Cataloging \(CVRMC\)](#)
 - Maintained by the ALA Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) Rare Books and Manuscripts Section (RBMS) the (CVRMC) is a genre/form terms vocabulary that includes a section of genre terms for [prejudicial materials](#), useful for indexing works that are prejudicial in nature, or that are the byproduct of prejudicial and hateful systems and ideologies. These terms are intended for collocating resources for research on the study of oppression, as well as to help metadata workers surface the essential nature of resources rather than contributing to or masking harm. Beyond the rare materials cataloging community, these terms can be used to identify biases and harmful content. New terms are added to the CVRMC at the request of community members using a [proposal form](#) and are vetted for inclusion by the RBMS Controlled Vocabularies Editorial Group.

Highlighted Resource: Controlled Vocabularies outside of Library of Congress

[Controlled Vocabularies \(CV\) Decision Tree](#) is a framework developed by the Samvera Metadata Interest Group, which provides guidance on evaluating, selecting and using controlled vocabularies. Though it is Samvera-specific, the general principles of these guidelines can be applied by anyone to evaluate if a particular controlled vocabulary is a good fit for use in a system.

6.3 Creating Local Controlled Vocabularies

While using an existing controlled vocabulary is ideal for metadata standardizing, there are cases where you may need to create a local controlled vocabulary to cover subjects missing from or misrepresented in the available existing vocabularies. While local vocabularies enable you to control precisely the terms applied to your records, they require regular maintenance and can cause complications during record-sharing with aggregators or other institutions, which must be accounted for in resourcing.

Highlighted Resources: Creating Local Controlled Vocabularies

[Diversity, equity and inclusion principles for custom taxonomies](#) discusses the common challenges and considerations associated with the development of custom taxonomies for describing people along the lines of race, gender, sexual orientation, nationality and other identity facets. Most appropriate for a Digital Asset Management System (DAMS) context, and includes examples.

[Improving Subject Headings for Iowa Indigenous People](#) is a working group paper from the Metadata Services department of the Iowa State University Libraries, which undertook a project to build, publish, and use a controlled vocabulary of preferred terms for Indigenous communities with ties to land that is now part of the state of Iowa.

7. Harmful Language and Content Statements

Filtered view in Resources Directory for: [Harmful Language and Content Statements](#) resources.

In recent years, a wave of institutions have made public statements on inclusive metadata topics such as ethical cataloging, harmful language, and reparative description. When harmful description or content may be encountered, a harmful language or content statement can provide context and warning to users.

These statements may be made at the aggregator, institutional, collection, or item level. They can inform people that they might encounter harmful language or content, share what the institution is or is not prepared to do about harmful description or content, and solicit feedback from users. Care should be taken when applying statements on harmful language or content to entire collections or adding statements in bulk to individual items, since the over-application of general statements at collection- or item-level can itself cause harm or confusion.

Aggregator and institution-wide harmful language statements or policies are web pages not associated with a specific collection or item. These statements often include institutional background, context of the archives and this work. They might take the form of a policy or a positionality statement.

Collection statements are used when an entire collection or sub-collection is known to or suspected of having harmful content. These statements can be added to the collection's description field or communicated via a pop up message, depending on the content and system used.

Item statements are applied on the individual digital content item level. These are often added to the description field of the record, but exact placement depends on the system. Item-level statements should be specific to the content of the item and contextualize its harmful content or language.

Considerations when evaluating and/or writing harmful language statements:

- Where on the page or within the repository is the statement located, and how does the user come into contact with it?
- How plain is the language?
- What is the framing of the statement – does it acknowledge non-neutrality and the role of institutions and individuals?
- Is it clear who created/published the statement and when?
- What kinds of contact/feedback mechanisms are provided?

- Does the statement distinguish between harmful language found in metadata descriptions vs. the content itself?
- What is the scope of the statement – what kinds of materials and collections are covered by it?
- Is the statement appropriately contextualized and specific to the materials covered by the statement, especially if it is an item-level statement?

Goals for your institution-level statement (from a 2022 [SAA webinar on Reparative Description](#) taught by Stephanie Luke and Sharon Mizota):

- Acknowledge harm; be specific about the types of content in your collections that may cause harm
- Acknowledge bias in your catalog/institution
- Assert that your institution maintains historical accuracy while mitigating harm
- Differentiate between transcribed metadata and that created by the institution
- Acknowledge that reparative description is a work in progress
- Provide an avenue for users to report harmful language or content

7.1 Example harmful language and content statements

Figure 1. Screenshot of [DPLA's Statement on Potentially Harmful Content](#), accessed August 12, 2024.

An example of an aggregator-level statement, the DPLA's Statement on Potentially Harmful Content (figure 1) includes the following text:

The Digital Public Library of America (DPLA) is a portal to millions of freely available items from thousands of libraries, archives, museums, and other cultural heritage organizations across the United States.

DPLA contains some content that may be harmful or difficult to view. Our cultural heritage partners collect materials from history, as well as artifacts from many cultures and time periods, to preserve and make available the historical record. As a result, some of the materials presented here may reflect outdated, biased, offensive, and possibly violent views and opinions due to pervasive systemic intolerance. In addition, some cultural heritage institutions collect and preserve materials relating to violent or graphic events which are preserved for their historical significance.

Following this statement, a frequently asked questions section outlines information such as where the material originates from, why it is included, what kinds of harmful content may be encountered, and how to contact DPLA about harmful content and description.

The screenshot shows the website interface for 'recollection WISCONSIN'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Partners', 'Blog', and 'Contact', and a search bar with the text 'Search the collection' and a 'SEARCH' button. Below the navigation bar is a main menu with four categories: 'EXPLORE', 'PROJECTS', 'TOOLKIT', and 'GET INVOLVED'. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: 'Home > Listening to War: Wisconsin's Wartime Oral Histories > Listening to War: Harmful Content Statement'. The title 'Listening to War: Harmful Content Statement' is prominently displayed. The text explains that some interviews in the 'Listening to War: Wisconsin's Wartime Oral Histories' collection contain descriptions of violence, injury, disease, mental distress, and other trauma. It also states that the interviews reflect a wide range of individual speakers' experiences, viewpoints, and time periods, and that Recollection Wisconsin rejects these biased views. A contact email 'info@recollectionwisconsin.org' is provided for reporting harmful content. A sidebar on the right contains a photo of soldiers and a list of links under the heading 'About the Project', including 'Collection Home Page', 'Acknowledgments', 'Content Contributors', 'Related Resources', 'Project Background', 'Harmful Content Statement', and 'Terms of Use'.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the harmful content statement for the [Listening to War collection of Recollection Wisconsin](#), accessed August 15, 2024.

The Listening to War: Harmful Content Statement from the Listening to War collection of [Recollection Wisconsin](#) (figure 2) is an example of a collection-specific statement. It contains specific information about the types of harmful content that may be encountered, places this content within its historical context, and provides contact information to report offensive or harmful content or language. It includes the following text:

Users are advised that some of the interviews in Listening to War: Wisconsin's Wartime Oral Histories contain descriptions of violence, injury, disease, mental distress, and other trauma. This includes eyewitness accounts of wartime combat and its aftermath as well as first-hand experiences of refugee camps, concentration camps, and prisoner-of-war camps.

In addition, the interviews presented here reflect a wide range of individual speakers' experiences, viewpoints, and time periods. Users may encounter harmful language, including the depiction of racist or hateful attitudes toward marginalized communities and the use of terms that are outdated, insensitive, or offensive. Recollection Wisconsin rejects these biased views; however, we recognize that these viewpoints illustrate social mindsets and perspectives of their time.

If you encounter language or content in this collection that you find offensive or harmful, please contact us at info@recollectionwisconsin.org. We will forward your report to the organization(s) that have contributed content to the collection.

Statement adapted from the Black Women's Suffrage Digital Collection Harmful Language Statement (Digital Public Library of America) and the Digital Collection Offensive Language Policy (Presbyterian Historical Society).

The next example (figure 3) is from University of Texas Arlington Libraries, which includes an early 20th century postcard that contains a derogatory and dehumanizing term used by settlers for Indigenous women that is printed on the original source material. While the metadata record's Title has been altered to exclude the harmful term on the item, the offensive term is noted in brackets within the Description. There is also a harmful content statement that appears in the lower right corner of the record reading:

Harmful Content Statement: This item includes content that may have outdated language or may be graphic or disturbing in nature. Please refer to our Statement of Harmful Language [linked to broader statement] for more information.

home > item: postcard illustration of a sioux woman

ITEM: POSTCARD ILLUSTRATION OF A SIOUX WOMAN

Brief Description Full Description Cite This Item

Identifier: 10021366

Title: Postcard illustration of a Sioux woman

Description: Postcard illustration of an indigenous Sioux woman. Postcard addressed to Eva Moore, postmarked July 16, 1910. [Note: The term "Squaw," which appears in the postcard's caption, is a derogatory term that has been used for Native American women since the 16th century.]

Date Created: 1910-07-16

Coverage: 1910s

Category: Architecture, Art and Culture

Subject: Sioux Nation Traditional dress Postcards

Indigenous peoples Indigenous women

Collection: Eva Moore Postcards Collection

Special Collections Identifier: AR571

Rights and License: [View Rights and License](#)

Harmful Content Statement: This item includes content that may have outdated language or may be graphic or disturbing in nature. Please refer to our [Statement of Harmful Language](#) for more information.

Figure 3. Screenshot of "[Postcard illustration of a Sioux woman](#)", from the University of Texas Arlington Libraries Digital Gallery, accessed August 22, 2024.

Highlighted Resources: Statements on Metadata and Archival Collections

The Cataloging Lab has compiled a [list of examples of both institutional and collection statements](#).

[Toward Ethical and Inclusive Descriptive Practices](#) details a case study about how the Collection Management unit at UCLA Library Special Collections went about crafting their descriptive practices statement, providing a model for how other institutions can do the same.

8. Maintenance Plan for This Project

The Toolkit guide document will be saved as a PDF and uploaded to the [DLF's Open Science Framework \(OSF\) repository](#). Working drafts from the development of the Toolkit are in the DLF/CAWG-AIG Google Drive, maintained by DLF.

The [Inclusive Metadata Toolkit Resources Directory spreadsheet](#) will be available as a dynamic resource. To submit additions to the Resources Directory, please [propose additions via this form](#) through the end of December 2026. The expected sunset date for the Resources Appendix is January 2027. At that time the spreadsheet data will be saved as a CSV file and added to the OSF deposit.

Maintainers will be responsible for:

- Maintaining the Inclusive Metadata Toolkit Resource Directory spreadsheet in Google Sheets
- Monitoring form for suggested additions, adding resources when approved by the CAWG
- At sunset of project, exporting data to CSV files and adding to OSF

Maintainers for this project from September 2024-December 2026 will be: Morgan McKeehan and the CAWG co-facilitators.